

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Mapping of Potential Stakeholders
and engagement strategy ready for CDEP
Milestone M6.1**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Milestone M6.1

Contact details

Project Office: esiwace3@bsc.es

Website: www.esiwace.eu

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/esiwace>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@esiwace880>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/esiwace3>

Vimeo: <https://www.vimeo.com/esiwace>

ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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Lead Beneficiary:

Barcelona Supercomputing Center-Centro Nacional de Supercomputación (BSC-CNS), Rosa Rodríguez Gasén

Other contributing authors:

The whole ESiWACE3 Consortium

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)
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Sveriges Meteorologiska Och Hydrologiska Institut (SMHI)
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Type:

Mapping

Dissemination level:

PU (for public use)

Delivery date:

Due date in month 6. Actual delivery date 30 June 2023.

Means of verifications:

A live document available in the project's wiki

Achieved:

Yes

If not achieved, indicate forecast achievement date:

-

Comments:

The current and potential network of stakeholders interested in the project results has been mapped. This mapping and the subsequent engagement strategy are live documents available in the project's wiki and will be updated during the project whenever necessary. The document is available [here](#).

Figure 1 shows the mapping of the current and potential stakeholders. According to this figure, the main target groups for the communication and dissemination activities are identified below:

- Scientific community (Earth System modellers)
- HPC community
- Training participants
- HPC industry (HPC technologists, technology providers, high-capacity data experts...)
- EuroHPC/EC ecosystem (European digital agenda-related initiatives, CoEs, NCCs, ...)
- Policy-makers

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Figure 1. Mapping of current and potential stakeholders.

In addition, an analysis of community engagement activities conducted in previous ESiWACE phases (e.g. through interviews and surveys) has also been conducted to assess successful actions and those that would require improvement. The results of this analysis are helping shape the engagement strategy of ESiWACE3, which will subsequently inform the CDEP updates.

The survey is available at <https://bsc3.typeform.com/surveycommunity>. In figure 2 a screenshot of the main page of the survey can be found.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the main page of the survey conducted among the ESiWACE community.

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And a screenshot of the recorded interviews conducted among the main leaders of ESiWACE, ESiWACE2, and ESiWACE3 can be seen in Figure 3:

Figure 3. Recorded interviews to learn more about the different phases of ESiWACE.

- 2023-05-24 10.03.54 ESiWACE3 interview - Joachim Biercamp

- 2023-05-16 14.37.32 ESiWACE3 interview - Erwan Raffin

- 2023-05-11 09.33.42 ESiWACE3 interview - Fanny Adloff

- 2023-05-10 10.04.45 ESiWACE3 interview - Peter Dueben

- 2023-05-09 11.01.56 ESiWACE3 interview - Sophie Valcke

- 2023-04-28 13.07.59 ESiWACE3 interview - Mario Acosta